

1 **Alpine peatlands: a multisensory pipeline allows for harmonised detection and** 2 **reveals widespread degradation in the European Alps**

3 Marian Schönauer^{1,*}, Elizaveta Avoiani², Douglas L. Godbold¹, Boris Rewald¹

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5 ¹ Department of Forest Protection and Wildlife Management, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, Mendel
6 University in Brno, 613 00 Brno, Czech Republic

7 ² Department of Forest Management and Applied Geoinformatics, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, Mendel
8 University in Brno, 613 00 Brno, Czech Republic

9 * Corresponding author, marian.schoenauer@mendelu.cz; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2179-2898>

10 **Abstract**

11 Alpine peatlands are critical, disproportionate carbon sinks and biodiversity reservoirs, yet their small size,
12 rugged terrain, and rapid change hamper consistent mapping and monitoring. We developed a cross-country,
13 multi-sensor workflow for the Central European Alps, to detect peatlands and diagnose where peatlands
14 may be degraded. More than 600 ground-truth polygons were selected from >1,500 mapped, multinational
15 sites, after applying a minimum-mapping unit (4 pixels \approx 1,700 m²). We investigated the best combination
16 of Sentinel-2 optical features, Sentinel-1 backscatter, Landsat-8 surface temperature, and terrain metrics
17 using a ridge regression model in a k-fold cross-validation, noting F β -scores, alongside false-negative
18 (FNR) and false-positive (FPR) rates. The best configuration (Sentinel-1 + Sentinel-2 + terrain) achieved a
19 mean F_{0.5} of 0.415 ± 0.290 ; with optical features dominating the model. Mean FNR (0.575 ± 0.311)
20 substantially exceeded FPR (0.0369 ± 0.0332), indicating that the model misses peatland pixels from the
21 ground-truth—especially where orthophotos reveal disturbances such as forest encroachment or
22 agricultural use. Apparent “false positives” often coincide with plausible unmapped peatlands. Aggregating
23 divergencies between predictions and ground-truth in \sim 250 km² hexagons produced a hotspot layer that
24 prioritizes re-monitoring, boundary refinement. This scalable, open workflow enables harmonised, cross-
25 border peatland updates in complex mountain terrain and provides policy-ready products to target
26 conservation and restoration where high-elevation carbon sinks and biodiversity hotspots are most at risk.

27 **Keywords:** Alpine areas, land cover, classification, moor, peatland, mire, draining, degradation, remote
28 sensing

29 **Introduction**

30 Global peatlands occupy around 400–480 million ha, occurring at all altitudes (Melton et al., 2022; United
31 Nations Environment Programme, 2024). Peatlands are among the most carbon-dense ecosystems, storing
32 ~30% of the world's soil organic carbon, despite covering only ~3% of the land. Intact peatlands (i.e. mires)
33 are at least seasonally water-saturated and range from rain-fed, acidic bogs (ombrotrophic) to groundwater-
34 fed, more base-rich fens (minerotrophic), with gradual transitions (Wheeler & Proctor, 2000). Peatlands
35 play a crucial role in maintaining water availability and quality (Rydin et al., 2013) and support specialised,
36 often rare biota (Chytrý et al., 2020; IUCN, 2021). However, these ecosystem services decline if peatlands
37 are drained, converted, and used intensively (Bundesamt für Naturschutz, 2024; Ministero dell'Ambiente
38 e della Sicurezza Energetica, 2025; Tanneberger et al., 2021). About 50% of EU peatlands and ~12%
39 globally are degraded and remain less protected than other high-value ecosystems (Austin et al., 2025;
40 Tanneberger et al., 2021; United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). Accurate, standardized mapping
41 of peatland extent and function is therefore essential for conservation/restoration and for assessing climate
42 and land-use impacts (Evans & Malcom, 2021; Minasny et al., 2024; Nordbeck & Høgl, 2024). This need
43 is heightened by potential biases in national statistics: protected peatlands were often designated as “best
44 examples,” while many smaller peatlands of unknown condition remain unmapped (Chimner et al., 2019;
45 Essl & Steiner, 2017).

46 Several global peatland maps have emerged in recent years (Minasny et al., 2024), but most aggregate
47 diverse and incompatible national datasets or rely on coarse (1–10 km) modelling approaches (Melton et
48 al., 2022; United Nations Environment Programme, 2024; Xu et al., 2018). These heterogeneous sources
49 hinder cross-country comparability and are not well suited to capturing the fine-scale fragmentation typical
50 of mountain peatlands. Alpine peatlands, occurring in the Andes, Himalayas, Rockies, Australian Alps and
51 European Alps, remain particularly poorly characterised and are consistently under-represented in global
52 inventories (Chen et al., 2014; Gaffney et al., 2025; Li et al., 2025). These peatlands are typically small
53 (<1-5 ha), scattered, characterized by extreme topography, variable climate, and glacial history. In contrast
54 to other Central European peatland systems, for example, Alpine mires are particularly coined by cold,
55 humid conditions and a short growing season, with annual precipitation often >1,000 mm and dominated
56 by snow (Sekulová et al., 2013). While key to regional hydrology and carbon cycling, and harbouring
57 endemic biota (e.g. Drollinger et al., 2019; Gaffney et al., 2025; Gerdol et al., 2011; United Nations
58 Environment Programme, 2024), many alpine peatlands have vanished or are degrading (for Austria see
59 e.g. Ellmauer et al. (2019)). For example, base-rich fens (FFH habitat type 7230) are among the most
60 species-rich yet most threatened ecosystems in the European Alps (Schrautzer & Martens, 2025). Alpine
61 peatlands are particularly sensitive to climate change and land-use pressures (Gobiet et al., 2014; Pullens

62 et al., 2016; Van der Knaap et al., 2011). Warming or drainage promotes drying and replacement of
63 characteristic peatland taxa by grassland or forest species (Bragazza & Gerdol, 1996; Brancaleoni & Gerdol,
64 2014). As peat accumulation occurs within a narrow climatic window, high-elevation peatlands are
65 especially vulnerable (Gaffney et al., 2025; Planas-Clarke et al., 2020). Additional degradation pressures
66 include fragmentation, infrastructure, and overgrazing (Sjögren et al., 2007; Spitale, 2021).

67 Remote sensing offers a promising pathway for upscaling peatland monitoring. Advances in cloud
68 computing and the availability of Sentinel-1/2, Landsat, LiDAR and high-resolution DEMs have enabled
69 flexible, cross-scale peatland classification pipelines (De Waard et al., 2024; Minasny et al., 2024). Optical
70 indices such as NDVI and NDWI serve as proxies for vegetation and moisture, while SAR is sensitive to
71 surface roughness and moisture dynamics (Barrett et al., 2009; Bhatnagar et al., 2020; Lees et al., 2020).
72 Yet fundamental uncertainties persist: (1) Which combinations of multisensory Earth observation data best
73 capture the unique spectral, structural and hydrological traits of peatlands in rugged mountain terrain? (2)
74 How do site attributes, peatland size, altitude, and local topography affect detectability? (3) How do
75 disturbances such as forestry, drainage, agriculture or infrastructure alter spectral signatures, and do they
76 impede peatland detection? (4) Can misclassifications be interpreted mechanistically to identify unmapped
77 or degrading peatlands?

78 These questions remain unanswered because Alpine peatlands pose distinctive challenges. Cloud and snow
79 cover limit optical observations; steep slopes, mixed pixels and sub-hectare peatland patches complicate
80 classification; and the spectral contrast between peatlands and surrounding vegetation is often reduced in
81 cool, humid mountain climates (Chimner et al., 2019; Li et al., 2025). Medium-resolution (≤ 30 m) remote
82 sensing products tend to underperform in detecting small, linear or fragmented peatland complexes
83 (Gallego, 2004; Minasny et al., 2019), and single-sensor approaches are intrinsically constrained by
84 moisture dependence (SAR), phenology (optical), or scale (thermal) (DeLancey et al., 2019; Krzepak et al.,
85 2022). Further, ground-truth datasets across countries vary widely in resolution, update frequency and
86 classification schemes, limiting the generalisability of regional or continental models (Karlson & Bastviken,
87 2023; Röschel et al., 2020).

88 Motivated by these challenges, we present an open, harmonised, transnational workflow for detecting
89 Alpine peatlands using multisensor Earth observation data across 626 peatlands in the Central European
90 Alps. Specifically, we:

- 91 (i) develop and benchmark a generalisable detection pipeline using Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Landsat-8 and
92 terrain metrics, and quantify feature importance to reveal the dominant spectral interactions underlying
93 peatland detectability in mountainous areas;
- 94 (ii) assess how peatland size, elevation and local topography influence detection accuracy;
- 95 (iii) reconcile model–map mismatches by examining whether false negatives / positives correspond to
96 degradation signals or unmapped peatlands, respectively; and
- 97 (iv) identify priority regions in the European Alps where ground surveys or boundary refinement are most
98 urgently needed.

99 Our study advances the mechanistic understanding of how peatlands manifest in remote-sensing space,
100 clarifies the limitations and opportunities for Alpine peatland detection, and provides an extensible open
101 framework for monitoring and restoration planning across mountain ranges.

102 **Material and Methods**

103 **Study region and ground-truth peatlands**

104 The study area is situated within the Central European Alps (total bounds of the reference data, west-east:
105 6.2°- 15.5°, south-north: 45.9° - 48.0°; EPSG:4326), and incorporates ground-truth peatlands located in
106 Austria, Germany, Italy and Switzerland (**Figure 1**, Table 1). Peatlands in the French Alps were considered,
107 but were not included due to insufficient data (Pinault et al., 2023). The study region consists mainly of
108 mountainous terrain ranging from 380 to 2,570 m a.s.l. This area receives an annual mean precipitation of
109 1,500–2,700 mm yr⁻¹ in much of the Alps, with dry regions receiving 500–950 mm yr⁻¹, and mean
110 temperatures ranging from -6°C to 12°C (European Environment Agency, 2009). The Alps are the
111 southernmost important area for European peatlands (region ‘X’) and the vegetation differs markedly from
112 that in other European peatland regions (Montanarella et al., 2006; Tanneberger et al., 2021). The vegetation
113 of Alpine bogs and fens is diverse, depending on bedrock and hydrology. See Chytrý et al. (2020) for
114 characteristic vegetation according to EUNIS habitat types and their (estimated) occurrence in the European
115 Alps (<https://floraveg.eu/habitat/overview/Q>).

116

117 **Figure 1.** Study area with 626 mapped peatlands in the European Alps used as reference data (A). Data
 118 was derived from governmental biotope mappings and Natura-2000 catalogues (Table 1). The inset (B)
 119 shows the spatial data used for modelling, for example Sentinel-2 Band 8, for the peatland (blue outline)
 120 and the surrounding 200 m buffer area (in colour; see text for details)

121

122 The peatland dataset, which was compiled in early 2025, consists of government biotope mapping from
 123 Austria, Germany, Italy and Switzerland and used as ground-truth data. This includes inventories provided
 124 by federal or regional authorities including the Natura 2000 network (Table 1). The peatlands in Italy were
 125 digitized manually, using Google Satellite and selected Natura 2000 points. To narrow the biotope types
 126 within the available datasets to the EUNIS class ‘Mires, bogs and fens’, the datasets were filtered using
 127 keywords identified by scanning the attributes (Table 1). After merging the filtered shapefiles of different
 128 sources (Table 1), a subset of 702 peatlands was selected, with the aim of achieving a homogeneous spatial
 129 density across the entire experimental area. The median size of the selected peatlands was 1.71 ha [$\equiv 1.71$
 130 $\times 10^4$ m²], with the first and third quantiles at 0.44 ha and 5.97 ha, respectively (Table 1). Applying a
 131 minimum-mapping unit (~0.17 ha; see ‘Modelling and analysis’) yielded 626 evaluation sites. The surveyed
 132 peatlands varied in altitude from 380 to 2,570 m a.s.l..

133

134 **Table 1.** Datasets used to identify peatlands in the European Alps of Austria (AT), Germany (DE), Italy
 135 (IT) and Switzerland (CH) (Central Alps). The selected search terms for filtering out peatlands of the
 136 biotope mapping are given (in German). In case of pure peatland maps, the filtering did not apply. Total
 137 frequency is given by ‘count’, statistics of area per peatland are given in hectare [ha \equiv 10⁴ m²]; 5th (P5)
 138 and 95th percentile (P95) are given. The compiled shapefiles have been made available (Schönauer, 2025).

Country	Source	Search terms	count	Area [ha]		
				P5	median	P95
AT	(Land Kärnten, 2024)	Lebendes Hochmoor	9	0.20	0.77	4.8
	(Land Steiermark, 2011)	*moos	3	6.07	9.36	12.4
	(Land Steiermark, 2014)	Naturnahe lebende Hochmoore, Lebende Hochmoore, Naturnahe lebende Hochmoore	14	0.37	0.95	22.4
	(Land Steiermark, 2007)	Moor (dystroph/oligotrophe Verlandungsserie)	64	0.18	1.23	8.9
	(Land Salzburg, 2015)	Hochmoore	7	0.52	5.46	23.8
	(Amt der Tiroler Landesregierung, 2022)	Hochmoorvegetation, gehölzfrei	86	0.04	0.26	2.9
	(DORIS, 2010)	-	48	0.02	0.84	8.0
DE	(Wittnebel et al., 2023)	Hochmoorboden	103	1.58	9.94	123.2
IT	(Autonome Provinz Bozen, 2024)	-	40	0.1	0.56	4.19
CH	(Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2021)	-	322	0.17	2.21	16.5
	(Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU, 2017)	-	6	0.41	2.17	26.7

139

140 *Annotation of disturbances*

141 Following a manual inspection of optical images such as government-provided orthophotos or Google
 142 satellite images, potential drivers of degradation were annotated. If disturbances were detected within the
 143 mapped peatland area, the following classes were ascertained:

- 144 • 'Agriculture' (visible mowing of grassland, cattle, and cattle trampling paths),
- 145 • 'Ditch' (visible drainage ditches),
- 146 • 'Forest' (visible forest cover on >30% of the area), and
- 147 • 'Infrastructure' (visible built-up areas, including roads and houses).

148 Selection of several classes was possible. We created the variable ‘Disturbance’ based on these drivers,
 149 setting it to “true” if any of the four classes applied to the mapped peatland area.

150 **Satellite data**

151 For each location, we downloaded a set of data, including Sentinel-1 (S1) and Sentinel-2 (S2) products
152 from the Copernicus programme of the European Space Agency (ESA Copernicus, 2025a, 2025b), Landsat
153 8 (L8) images for surface temperature (U.S. Geological Survey, 2025), land cover maps, and a digital
154 elevation model (see section below). A 200 m buffer (in N, S, E, W directions) was added for each peatland
155 (see Figure 1B), and the total boundary of this buffer defined the area of interest (AOI) when downloading
156 spatial data via the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform’s API (Gorelick et al., 2017; Wu, 2020). To avoid
157 satellite image overlap, adjacent peatlands within a 200 m radius were unified into multipolygons before
158 the buffer was added. This process resulted in 317 multipolygons and reduced the set of 702 peatlands to
159 317 AOIs used for the data download. Within the GEE portal, the output resolution was set to (scale =)
160 0.0002°, which gave rasters with an average spatial resolution of 17.65 m, ranging from 15.65 to 20.71 m
161 (in EPSG 32633), depending on the geographic position of the AOI. We chose this resolution as a medium
162 size between 10 m for S1 radar and selected S2 bands, S2 bands with 20 m resolution (i.e. bands 8A, 11
163 and 12), 100 m L8-TIRS and the 30-m DEM. A five-year time series (2019–2023) was generated using all
164 available acquisitions. We also tested acquisitions from the vegetation period only to ensure consistency
165 across seasons and reduce the impact of snow and ice, which are common in alpine regions (Asam et al.,
166 2018). However, integrating year-round data resulted in better modelling performance (data not shown).

167 *Sentinel-1 data*

168 Sentinel-1 VV and VH backscatter data were sourced from the GEE COPERNICUS/S1_GRD Image
169 Collection. This collection has already undergone the standard ESA GRD preprocessing chain (ESA
170 Copernicus, 2025b; *Sentinel-1 SAR GRD*, n.d.), including orbit file application (using restituted or precise
171 metadata), GRD border noise removal, thermal noise removal, and radiometric calibration to convert raw
172 digital numbers to backscatter coefficients (σ^0). In addition to the geometrical terrain correction to ground-
173 range geometry using the SRTM 30 m DEM, we also applied the radiometric terrain correction according
174 to Vollrath et al. (2020), giving S1-data in decibels (dB). To mitigate speckle noise in SAR imagery, while
175 preserving edges and details in spatially variable regions, we applied the Lee Sigma filter (DeLancey et al.,
176 2019; Lee et al., 1994).

177 To enhance the input data further, we calculated radar-derived indices from the dual-polarized Sentinel-1
178 backscatter data. These indices are the Cross-Polarization Ratio (R_c , X. Hu et al., 2024), and the Radar
179 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (RNDVI, Mastro et al., 2023), according to equations (1) and (2),
180 respectively (Table 2). In these equations, VH denotes the cross-polarized and VV denotes the co-polarized
181 backscatter intensities. These indices provide complementary information on vegetation structure,
182 scattering behaviour, and moisture conditions (X. Hu et al., 2024). Analogous to optical NDVI (see below),

183 the RNDVI captures relative differences in the backscatter response, helping distinguish between varying
184 canopy densities and peatland moisture regimes (Mastro et al., 2023).

185 *Sentinel-2 data*

186 Sentinel-2 (S2) Level-2A surface reflectance data were sourced from the GEE COPERNICUS/S2_SR
187 Image Collection. The cloud masking algorithm QA60 was applied, supporting cloud and shadow filtering,
188 with a threshold set to 20%. Bands 3 (Green), 8 (Near Infrared), 8A (Red Edge 4), 11 and 12 (Short-Wave
189 Near Infrared) were selected for analysis (Table 2). Bands were selected for their sensitivity to peatland
190 conditions (Mahdianpari et al., 2019) and checked for high auto-correlations. Band 3 distinguishes surface
191 water and vegetation. Bands 8 and 8A highlight healthy and structurally varied vegetation. Bands 11 and
192 12 detect moisture and soil changes, useful for identifying drying, rewetting, or surface exposure.
193 Additionally, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI, NASA Earth Observatory, 2000; Tucker,
194 1979) and two types of the Normalized Difference Water Index, (NDWI_McF, McFeeters, 1996) and
195 (NDWI_Gao, Gao, 1996) were calculated according to equations (3), (4) and (5), where ‘BX’ denotes the
196 bands of Sentinel-2 products (Table 2).

197 *Landsat 8 data*

198 Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS) surface reflectance data provided by Landsat 8 (L8) were sourced from
199 the GEE LANDSAT/LC08/C02/T1_L2 Image Collection, provided by the U.S. Geological Survey (2025).
200 Preprocessing was applied to ensure data quality and radiometric consistency following the standard USGS
201 Collection 2 Level-2 workflow. This included (1) masking of fill values, clouds, and cloud shadows using
202 the QA_PIXEL band; (2) removal of saturated pixels using the QA_RADSAT band; and (3) application of
203 scale and offset coefficients from the image metadata to convert raw digital numbers into temperature
204 values, as described by the GEE Team (2025). The resulting L8 images provide atmospherically corrected
205 surface temperature layers.

206

207 **Table 2.** Description of input variables derived from Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and Landsat 8, as well as the
 208 Digital Elevation Model (DEM) GLO-30. Parameters include the VV and VH backscatter intensity
 209 channels and their ratio (Rc), (Radar) Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (RNDVI / NDVI),
 210 Normalized Difference Water Indices (NDWI_{McF} and NDWI_{Gao}). Surface Temperature ST_B10 was derived
 211 from L8. Topographic and hydrological variables are derived from DEM products. Note: Formulas are from
 212 Mastro et al. (2023) (S1); (Gao, 1996; McFeeters, 1996; NASA Earth Observatory, 2000) (S2); (U.S.
 213 Geological Survey, 2025) (ST_B10 conversion); (Lindsay, 2016; Sørensen et al., 2006; Wu & Brown,
 214 2022) (TWI); DTW were derived according to (Schönauer et al., 2021; Schönauer & Maack, 2025). S1 and
 215 S2 include all observations for the years 2019–2023, resampled to 0.0002°.

Group	Variable	Wavelength, method or formula	(#)
Sentinel-1 (<i>S1</i>)	VV	Synthetic Aperture Radar co-polarized intensity, lee- and terrain-corrected	
	VH	Synthetic Aperture Radar cross-polarized intensity, lee- and terrain-corrected	
	Rc	$Rc = VH / VV$	(1)
	RNDVI	$RNDVI = (VH - VV) / (VH + VV)$	(2)
Sentinel-2 (<i>S2</i>)	B3	Green (559.8 nm), harmonised surface reflectance	
	B8	NIR (832.8 nm), harmonised surface reflectance	
	B8A	Red Edge 4 (864.7 nm), harmonised surface reflectance	
	B11	SWIR1 (1613.7 nm), harmonised surface reflectance	
	B12	SWIR2 (2202.4 nm), harmonised surface reflectance	
	NDVI	$NDVI = (B8 - B4) / (B8 + B4)$	(3)
	NDWI _{McF}	$NDWI_{McF} = (B3 - B8A) / (B3 + B8A)$	(4)
	NDWI _{Gao}	$NDWI_{Gao} = (B8A - B11) / (B8A + B11)$	(5)
Landsat 8 (<i>L8</i>)	ST_B10	TIRS Band (10.60-11.19 μ m), surface temperature in [K]	(6)
DEM GLO-30 (<i>terrain</i>)	Elevation	in m	
	Slope	in %	
	TWI	$TWI = \ln(A / \tan(\text{slope}))$	(7)
	DoD	Depth of Depression = hydrologically filled DEM – DEM	(8)
	DTW1, 4 and 10	$DTW_i = [\sum \text{slope}_i \times s] \sqrt{s^2}$; for 1, 4 and 10 ha	(9)

216

217 Land cover maps, topographical data

218 Raster maps of ‘Dynamic World’ (Brown et al., 2022) for August 2023 were downloaded using the GEE’s
 219 API and aggregated, creating an Image with 1 layer. For downloading terrain data provided by Copernicus
 220 Digital Elevation Model ‘GLO-30’ (European Space Agency, 2024), a buffer of 1000 m was applied,

221 extending the AOI for this component of data. The larger buffer size was chosen to give more reliable
222 estimates for the topographic indices based on flow accumulation. One of these, the topographic wetness
223 index (TWI), was calculated using the programming language R (version 4.4.2, R Core Team, 2024) and
224 the package ‘whitebox’ (Lindsay, 2016; Wu & Brown, 2022), providing tools for creating hydrologically
225 corrected DEM, flow accumulations, terrain slope [%] and TWI (Equation 7, Table 2), where A is the
226 specific contributing area. TWI is a numerical indicator that quantifies the effect of topography on the
227 location and extent of wet areas. The hydrologically corrected DEM was also used to calculate Depth of
228 Depression (DoD [m]). Therefore, the original DEM was subtracted from the corrected one (Equation 8).
229 We also calculated depth-to-water (DTW) indices with different flow initiation areas (1, 4 and 10 ha),
230 giving the variables DTW1, DTW4 and DTW10. Those maps describe the vertical distance of a given DEM
231 pixel to the nearest flow line, where low values are supposed to reflect the tendency of areas to be water
232 saturated (Murphy et al., 2011). DTW maps were calculated (Equation 9), using the slope of a cell i , the
233 multiplier s integrating the cell size, and $\sqrt{s^2}$ for diagonally draining cells, following Schönauer & Maack
234 (2025) (version 3), using the R-package ‘terra’ (Hijmans, 2025).

235 **Transformation of satellite imagery and terrain data to modelling inputs**

236 To derive modelling inputs from the Sentinel and Landsat imagery along with the indices calculated, and
237 the terrain data, we processed the geospatial data (in NetCDF format, (Hoyer & Hamman, 2017))
238 consecutively for each AOI. After aligning S1, S2, L8, land classification and terrain data to common spatial
239 coordinates, the NetCDF objects were transformed into DataFrames (“pandas”, Pedregosa et al., 2011). For
240 the temporal input covering the five-year period, descriptive statistics were computed for each pair of
241 coordinates: mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum. This aggregation and associated reduction
242 in dimensionality of data was vital; from the e.g. S1 products, which initially contained 480 temporal layers,
243 the aggregation to mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values reduced the data size by a
244 factor of 120, thereby also supporting the creation of a general model by unifying the features. Afterwards,
245 all variables except the static information on land classification (Dynamic World) and altitude were
246 standardized for each AOI, using the ‘StandardScaler’ (Pedregosa et al., 2011).

247 By means of a spatial join, the stacked data was classified into peatland and non-peatland areas, using the
248 mapped peatlands as ground-truth. In case of multipolygons, we split up the non-peatland area. This means,
249 that the non-peatland (included in the buffer zone of each AOI) was randomly split and assigned to the
250 individual peatland-polygons included in the multipolygon.

251 Subsequently, we concatenated all DataFrames, excluded ‘water’ and ‘built-up’ areas classified by
252 Dynamic World, and reapplied standardisation (Pedregosa et al., 2011). This resulted in a DataFrame with

253 1,19 x 10⁶ rows, each representing a grid cell, out of which more than 200,000 were classified as peatland.
254 Sample weights were calculated as reciprocal values of square root of peatland and non-peatland size of
255 each polygon. Besides the sample weights, the data frame consisted of 67 independent variables, while the
256 spatial coordinates and the response variable (Boolean values of peatland/non-peatland) were integrated as
257 an index. The data was made available via GitHub ([URL](#) will be provided upon acceptance or request).

258 **Modelling and analysis**

259 We defined ten different settings to be analysed in this work (Figure 2A), given by different combinations
260 of the variable groups (**Table 2**):

- 261 • S1: included the variables 'VV', 'VH', 'RNDVI', and 'Rc',
- 262 • S2: 'B3', 'B8', 'B8A', 'B11', 'B12', 'NDVI', 'NDWI_{McF}', 'NDWI_{Gao}'
- 263 • L8: 'ST_B10', and
- 264 • terrain: 'elevation', 'slope', 'TWI', 'DoD', 'dtw01', 'dtw04', 'dtw10'.

265 Ridge regression models with alpha being 1 (Pedregosa et al., 2011) and sample weights assigned were
266 trained on the data following a polynomial preprocessing, including interactions and squares of all variables.
267 The training was done in a 10-fold cross validation, using the peatlands' ID as keys for partitioning. Model
268 coefficients (weights) of the individual ridge models were saved for later analysis. Predictions were made
269 on each of the 10th chunk of data, the un-seen testing partitions. After translating the pixel-wise predictions
270 to connected areas, positive predictions with an area smaller than the minimal mapping unit set to the size
271 of four grid cells (i.e. 1715 m², 4 x s², with s being the maximum grid cell size) were coerced to negative
272 predictions. Having both, actual *and* predicted values of classification of each raster cell, the performance
273 metrics were calculated after also filtering the peatlands of the ground-truth data by the minimum mapping
274 unit. This reduced the number of peatlands from 702 to 626 which were considered for reporting the
275 performance. We chose F_β with a β of 0.5 (i.e. 'F_{0.5}'; (Pedregosa et al., 2011)) as main metric to assess
276 performance. The F-score is used in classification tasks to evaluate a model's performance by combining
277 precision and recall into a single metric. A β of 0.5 means that it weights precision higher than recall. This
278 is useful when false positives are more costly than false negatives (which are already in mapped areas), for
279 example, when many areas are incorrectly classified as false positives, triggering peatland mapping
280 campaigns when there are very few actual cases across the landscape. In addition, false negative rates (FNR)
281 and false positive rates (FPR) were stored, calculated as $FNR = fn / (fn + tp)$ and $FPR = fp / (fp + tn)$,
282 respectively, with *fp* being the number of false positives, *fn* the number of false negatives, *tp* the number of
283 true positives, and *tn* the number of true negatives. F-scores were compared between different settings,
284 using related 2-sample t-tests, or correlated with terrain data using linear regression models (Virtanen et al.,

285 2020). Independent t-tests were used to compare FNR and FPR between disturbed and non-disturbed
286 peatlands. For identifying the contribution of each type of degradation, an ordinary least square regression
287 (Virtanen et al., 2020) was fit, followed by an analysis of variance with sum of squares set to type III. To
288 show regions of high FRN, we performed a spatial aggregation (Dahn, 2021), calculating mean values of
289 FNR and FPR within $\sim 250 \text{ km}^2$ hexagons. Only hexagons with ≥ 5 peatlands are displayed.

290 Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation or as median. The level of significance p was set to 0.05.
291 All analysis but the calculation of topographic indices were done in the programming language Python
292 (3.13.2, Van Rossum & Drake Jr, 1995) interfaced with Spyder (version 5, Raybaut, 2009) - the scripts
293 used have been made available on GitHub (URL will be provided upon acceptance or request). Predictions
294 as well as ground-truth peatlands have been made available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855356>
295 (Schönauer, 2025).

296

297 **Results**

298 In comparing the different combinations of multisensory input data for predicting 626 peatlands across the
299 Central European Alps, the configuration of Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 with terrain data achieved the highest
300 $F_{0.5}$ -score of 0.415 ± 0.290 , corresponding to a median of 0.443 (Figure 2A). The influence of surface
301 temperature from Landsat 8 appeared to be negligible, as adding surface temperature estimates resulted in
302 a nearly identical $F_{0.5}$ -score (median of 0.436). When only Sentinel-2 products and terrain data were used
303 for modelling, the predictive performance dropped slightly (paired t-test, $p = 0.003$) to 0.406 ± 0.291 ,
304 representing a 2.24% decrease.

305 Within the best-performing setting (S1 + S2 + terrain), the most influential model weight was associated
306 with the interaction between year-round averages of the Sentinel-2 bands B8 and B8A, followed by NDVI
307 (Figure 2), which was inversely related to the occurrence of peatlands. In third place, the interaction
308 between B8 and NDVI was found; in fifth, the optical NDWI according to McFeeters (1996), also showing
309 lower values on peatlands compared to the non-peatlands. The eleven most important model weights out of
310 almost 1,400 for this feature combination after pre-processing were given to optical bands, dominated by
311 B8, B8A, B4 (used in NDVI calculation only) and B3 (used for $NDWI_{McF}$), highlighting the importance of
312 the two near-infrared spectral bands and the reds.

313 Beyond the spectral signatures from Sentinel-2, the mean elevation of peatlands appeared with lower
314 importance, primarily in interaction with the two near-infrared bands (Figure 2). Sentinel-1-related features

315 were not among the top-20 features. The first occurrence was on 47th place, showing VV in interaction with
 316 B8A. This is also reflected by the low $F_{0.5}$ -scores of the setting S1, which averaged 0.0129 ± 0.0824 . When
 317 combining S1 with terrain, however, the $F_{0.5}$ -scores reached (0.177 ± 0.241) were clearly higher than those
 318 obtained when using S1 or terrain (0.114 ± 0.209) alone.

319

320

321 **Figure 2. A)** Boxplots show descriptive statistics of $F_{0.5}$ values for detecting peatlands in the European
 322 Alps according to different sets of input variables used. These sets comprise combinations of Sentinel-1
 323 and Sentinel-2 products (S1, S2, respectively), terrain data including slope, elevation, and topographic
 324 wetness index, depth-to-water indices and depth of depression (terrain), and surface temperature from
 325 Landsat-8 (L8). The best-performing model setting is marked in orange. **B)** The bar-plot illustrates the
 326 top-20 model weights (i.e. the coefficients of a Ridge regression model) for the best-performing set of
 327 input data (i.e. S1+S2+terrain), given as the average for a 10-fold cross-validation. See Table 2 for input
 328 parameters

329

330 Neither the broad altitudinal range of the study sites (from 380 m to 2,570 m a.s.l.) nor the slope of the
 331 surrounding terrain had a clear effect on modelling performance (Figure 3). However, performance in
 332 detecting peatlands clearly depended on their size, with accuracy increasing with size (Figure 3A).
 333 Accordingly, $F_{0.5}$ -scores for large peatlands (>5 ha) averaged 0.584 ± 0.249 , whereas those for peatlands
 334 between 1 and 5 ha were 0.434 ± 0.265 . Performance dropped further for peatlands with a size between 0.5
 335 and 1 ha (0.270 ± 0.235), and for those <0.5 ha (0.152 ± 0.199). This lower value is partly driven by the
 336 high proportion of near-zero $F_{0.5}$ -scores (i.e., <0.01), which occurred in 47.2% and 29.9% of cases for

337 peatlands sized up to 0.5 ha and 0.5-1 ha, respectively. However, with increasing size, the frequency of $F_{0.5}$
338 scores close to zero decreased to 4.33% for peatlands larger than 5 ha.

339

340 **Figure 3.** $F_{0.5}$ -scores of the best-performing model set (i.e. S1+S2+terrain) used in a Ridge regression
341 model are compared with **A)** the area of peatland ($\geq 1715 \text{ m}^2$), **B)** elevation and **C)** terrain slope. Linear
342 models were fit between the three parameters and $F_{0.5}$ -scores, correlation slopes given, and regression
343 lines illustrated in black ($p < 0.05$) and blue ($p \geq 0.05$; $n = 626$)

344

345 In most cases, $F_{0.5}$ -scores close to zero were caused by Type II errors, meaning that the model predicted
346 non-peatland areas (false negatives) where peatlands were mapped in the ground-truth data. Figure 4A
347 shows that high rates of false negatives (FNR) coincide with low $F_{0.5}$ scores. Similar distributions were
348 observed when comparing FNR with F_1 -scores (data not shown). Type I errors, in which the model predicts
349 a peatland where none is present in the ground-truth maps, can be quantified via the false positive rates
350 (FPR). The FPR were low with a mean of 0.0369 ± 0.0332 , as compared to the mean of FNR ($0.575 \pm$
351 0.311 ; paired t-test, $p < 0.001$), which suggests that there are currently fewer unmapped peatlands than
352 degraded peatlands.

353 Clear differences emerged when comparing the FNR of undisturbed and degraded peatlands. The latter
354 holding any visually identifiable disturbance such as agriculture, ditch, infrastructure and/or forest
355 encroachment (Figure 4C). FNR averaged 0.440 ± 0.303 for visually undisturbed peatlands (only 14.4% of
356 cases), and 0.598 ± 0.301 for disturbed peatlands. The impact of a present disturbance on FNR was stronger
357 for small peatlands, with sizes < 1 ha, where a 1.6-fold increase in FNR was observed. This difference
358 decreased with size class, being also significant for peatlands of 1-5 ha, but not for those sized 0.5-1 ha and
359 > 5 ha.

360

361 **Figure 4.** Scatterplots show the relationship between $F_{0.5}$ -scores and **A)** false negative rates (FNR, Type
 362 II errors), and **B)** false positive rates (FPR, Type I errors). The density of observations is indicated by
 363 shading. **C)** Boxplots summarize FNR distributions in relation to visible disturbances identified from
 364 recent orthophotos, separated by peatland size classes. Differences between FNR are given in the top, in
 365 bold when being significant (independent t-test). The number of sample sites per size and disturbance
 366 class is given next to the 75th percentile.

367

368 The prevalence of certain disturbance types varied: 58.6% of peatlands were affected by infrastructure
 369 (houses, roads), 45.0% by visible drainage ditches, 25.1% by agricultural land use (mowing, cattle, cattle
 370 trampling path), and 17.6% by forest cover ($\geq 30\%$). Disturbances of any kind were in sum detected on
 371 85.6% of peatlands, and often co-occurred (47.1%). The effect of specific disturbance types on the false-
 372 negative rate (FNR) differed (**Table 2**). An ANOVA indicated that FNR was driven mainly by 'Forest'
 373 (largest sum of squares), followed by 'Agriculture'. The effects of 'Infrastructure' and 'Ditch' were not
 374 statistically significant.

375

376

377 **Table 2.** Analysis of variance for an ordinary least-squares (OLS) model of false-negative rates (FNR)
 378 across disturbance drivers (forest cover, agricultural land use, constructed infrastructure, visible drainage
 379 ditches)

	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	F-value	p-value
Intercept	48.50	1	517.13	<0.001
Forest	1.05	1	11.15	<0.001
Agriculture	1.13	1	12.08	<0.001
Ditch	0.26	1	2.81	0.09
Infrastructure	0.10	1	1.03	0.31
Residual	58.25	621		

380

381 Although the effect of ‘Ditch’ on FNR-values was statistically not significant, we observed cases that merit
 382 follow-up with historical data. One such case is given by a peatland located in the state of Salzburg, Austria
 383 (Figure 55A), having a low $F_{0.5}$ -score of 0.0616. Despite its considerable mapped size (15.5 ha), the number
 384 of pixels with a positive model prediction was minimal, yielding an extremely high FNR (0.985)—i.e. a
 385 substantial proportion of Type II errors at this site. However, historical orthophotos (2007-2024) show
 386 progressive road construction and an expanding network of drainage ditches, providing visual evidence of
 387 ongoing disturbance and degradation (**Figure 5**Figure 5B-D). The peatland area appeared intensely green
 388 and undisturbed in 2007.

389

390 **Figure 5.** Peatland in Salzburg (state), Austria (at an elevation of 1800 m) according to official biotope
 391 mappings (Table 1; dark blue line in **A**). It was used as training data for modelling peatlands. Raster
 392 predictions of true values (S1+S2+terrain) are illustrated by a light blue outline. The yellow dashed area
 393 indicates the absence of predicted peatland, including within the 200 m buffer zone (cropped on image in
 394 N and S directions). Gaps in the shading are caused by missing Satellite data; GPS position is given.
 395 Historical orthophotos from 2007, 2012, and 2024 show the disturbance of the peatland caused by the
 396 construction of a road and a network of ditches (**B-D**)

397

398 Figure 6 illustrates the robustness and suitability of our modelling approach for peatland mapping. Panel A
 399 shows a high-elevation peatland in South Tyrol, Italy (2,300 m a.s.l.), which is well covered by positive
 400 predictions. However, arrow 1 marks an adjacent area to the east with a clear peatland signature in Google
 401 satellite imagery, which is absent from current peatland maps. Similarly, the positive detections (arrows 2,
 402 Figure 66B, Germany; $F_{0.5} = 0.655$) were present on a mapped non-peatland area, whereas this part shows
 403 the indications using orthophotos. Arrow 3 marks a recent road development that removed a small portion
 404 of the peatland, as well as part of an adjacent grassland area that is included in the official mapping.
 405 Although these changes in peatland extent are not yet reflected in the ground-truth map, our model captures
 406 them and they contribute to the site's FNR of 0.225.

407

408 **Figure 6.** Two examples illustrating peatland detection using a ridge regression model ($S1+S2+terrain$)
 409 trained on 626 peatlands distributed across the Alps on unseen data. **A)** Correct detection of an alpine
 410 peatland located in South Tyrol, Italy, at 2,300 m a.s.l., showing a potential eastern extension (arrow 1)
 411 with clear peatland characteristics not included in the official mapping. **B)** A small part of a peatland
 412 mapped in the Alpine Foreland of southern Germany (740 m a.s.l.) appears to have been missed (arrows
 413 2), while a road and agricultural land are partially included in official maps (arrows 3), but excluded by
 414 the model. GPS locations are given on images

415

416 Elevated rates of both false negatives may indicate out-of-date ground-truth data / degradation. By
 417 aggregating these scores, we can flag regions where model detections and maps diverge strongly (**Figure**
 418 **7**), thereby prioritising fieldwork to refine boundaries and degradation status. For example, in parts of the
 419 high elevation mountain range of eastern Switzerland, the region of Graubünden and Engadin, was
 420 attributed with FNR between 0.9 and 1 (**Figure 7**).

421

422 **Figure 7.** Spatial aggregations of false negative rates (FNR) calculated for detections made by a Ridge
 423 regression trained on government mapped peatlands across the European Alps. FNR are interpreted as an
 424 indicator of degradation of mapped peatlands. Hexagons (~ 250 km²) with less than 5 peatlands were
 425 omitted

426

427 Discussion

428 Alpine peatlands are of disproportionate value in terms of climate regulation and biodiversity. Their
 429 increasing exposure to climate change and land-use pressures makes them a landscape feature of high public
 430 interest. Still, the small scaled and scattered peatlands of mountainous landscapes are underrepresented in
 431 research due to their remote locations, which hinder access for mapping and follow-up monitoring. Our
 432 multi-sensor workflow produced a reproducible, cross-border approach for detecting Alpine peatlands and
 433 diagnosing likely degradation. The most effective sensor combination (Sentinel-1 + Sentinel-2 + terrain)
 434 was conservative in assigning peatland labels; however, many mapped peatland pixels are missed by the
 435 model especially where orthophotos indicate forest encroachment or agricultural use. Below we interpret
 436 these outcomes, reconcile prediction-ground-truth mismatches, and outline a policy-ready product to
 437 prioritise re-monitoring and restoration where global changes are rapidly transforming peatlands.

438 **Model performance and weights**

439 The best-performing model combined S1+S2+terrain inputs, with Sentinel-2 spectral features clearly
440 dominating model weights. In particular, the NIR (B8), Red Edge (B8A), and the red (B4) and green (B3)
441 bands that contribute to NDVI were the strongest predictors. NDVI is widely used for peatland detection
442 because it discriminates healthy vegetation from waterlogged or low-productivity areas typical of peatlands
443 (Chávez et al., 2023; Crichton et al., 2022). We also included the normalized difference water index
444 ($NDWI_{McF}$) to capture wet–dry gradients and seasonal water-level changes (Krizepek et al., 2022; McFeeters,
445 1996). However, $NDWI_{McF}$ showed a negative effect. When the Green–NIR $NDWI_{McF}$ (McFeeters, 1996)
446 is applied to dense vegetation it yields negative values, as vegetation reflects strongly in the NIR and only
447 moderate in the green band (B3). Consequently, the influence of surface water during waterlogged phases
448 must have been less important than anticipated, consistent with the findings of Gunawardhana et al., (2021).
449 They monitored water table depth of an Alpine peatland and report highest water levels at approximately -
450 200 mm, which would be beyond the detection capability of the optical Sentinel-2 sensor. We assume that
451 the more negative NDWI values were driven by denser vegetation in peatlands compared to nearby control
452 areas. A different configuration of NDWI, as defined by Gao et al. (1996), using NIR and SWIR bands, is
453 instead designed to be sensitive to foliar water content and should identify non-photosynthetically active or
454 pre–green-up peatland areas (Kalaeska et al., 2018). In this modelling, however, the importance of $NDWI_{Gao}$
455 has been limited, occurring on 41st place in the best settings’ feature ranking, compared to 5th for $NDWI_{McF}$.

456 The dense vegetation on the study areas is expected to result in a limited importance of S1 features (Bauer-
457 Marschallinger et al., 2019; Madelon et al., 2023). The S1-only setting achieved an $F_{0.5}$ -score of $0.0129 \pm$
458 0.0824 , indicating poor peatland detection when using C-band SAR alone. C-band penetration is
459 constrained under moderate to high vegetation cover, which both attenuates the radar signal and adds
460 canopy scattering that masks soil moisture signatures (Bazzi et al., 2023; Meyer et al., 2022). Nevertheless,
461 the best-performing setting ‘S1+S2+terrain’ benefited slightly when S1-features were included, suggesting
462 SAR contributes complementary structural information in open or sparsely vegetated peatlands. For
463 large-scale mapping, however, reducing the feature set to the most informative variables could streamline
464 computation load; in our pipeline the additional terrain correction of S1-parameters (Vollrath et al., 2020)
465 was particularly computation-intensive.

466 Model performance increased with peatland size: $F_{0.5}$ ranged from 0.152 ± 0.199 for small peatlands (0.17–
467 0.5 ha), to 0.434 ± 0.265 for 1–5 ha sites and 0.584 ± 0.249 for large peatlands. We argue that several
468 independent factors likely constrained higher scores: Firstly, the ground-truth dataset is heterogeneous and
469 may contain labelling errors and spatial misalignments. Secondly, temporal discrepancies between the
470 ground-truth maps and the 2019–2023 EO time series, combined with ongoing peatland degradation

471 resulting from establishing forest cover, drainage, grazing and infrastructure, can reduce apparent
472 consistency. Thirdly, our choice of true negatives (i.e. non-peatland areas sampled within the 200 m buffer
473 zone around mapped peatlands) intentionally reduced class separability, thereby lowering conventional
474 accuracy metrics. Although this selection of true negatives introduces additional challenges for modelling,
475 we state that this data selection is essential for a rigorous validation of the detection models. Contrarily,
476 peatland and non-peatland areas were selected manually for a recent study mapping peatlands in the Italian
477 Alps (Li et al., 2025). We hypothesise that differences in EO signals between peatlands and non-peatlands
478 increase with spatial distance and variations in land-use types, leading to an potential inflation of
479 performance. Likewise, models based on terrain data were created to detect peatlands in Nordic generally
480 homogeneous landscapes successfully (Rimondini et al., 2023; Vollerling et al., 2025), whereas ‘terrain’
481 features in this work (topographically heterogeneous Central Alps) contributed less to discrimination
482 (Figure 2A), likely due to the spatial proximity between both classes in this validation. Overall, our results
483 align with recent mapping efforts for the Tibetan Plateau (Pan et al. (2025)), applying an automated
484 selection of peatland and non-peatland – they similarly found NDVI and NDWI to be the most important
485 predictors, followed by Sentinel-2 bands.

486 **Comparison with official mappings and disturbance indicators**

487 Comparisons of our model detections with government peatland mapping show a clear pattern across
488 countries and elevations. Model agreement is strongest where sites remain visually undisturbed. Pixels of
489 “false” negatives are concentrated where disturbance-derived degradation has likely altered the vegetation
490 structure, surface moisture and/or the delineation of currently mapped peatland boundaries. Although
491 peatland degradation is widely reported across Europe (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024),
492 the frequency of disturbances that we recorded in the Central Alps is striking: visible signs of disturbance
493 occurred on ~86% of mapped peatlands. This figure should be regarded as a conservative lower bound of
494 actual degradation and helps explain the elevated false-negative rate, including at sites where no obvious
495 disturbance factors were recorded. Following a census of peatlands in South Tyrol, Göttlich (1991) reported
496 that only 6% of peatlands remained in a natural state. More recent work in the Italian Alps found a higher
497 (~35%), albeit still limited, proportion of intact peatlands (Spitale, 2021). Similar declines in intact
498 high-altitude peatlands have been documented in other regions, such as the Qinghai–Tibetan Plateau and in
499 the Andes (Benavides et al., 2013; Luan et al., 2014).

500 Most false negatives were spatially associated with peatlands showing clear degradation signals. Forest
501 encroachment was the most frequent correlate, followed by agricultural use (mowing, grazing). This is
502 consistent with the altered phenology in managed grasslands, and the spectral/backscatter ambiguity that
503 arises when peat soils are partially drained or overgrown. An ongoing degradation is reasonable as temporal

504 mismatch remains unavoidable: our EO composites and orthophoto acquisition years do not coincide with
505 the dates of official mapping. Operational thresholds for tree cover also affect classification and
506 interpretation. While scattered shrubs and trees are natural in some peatland types, operational definitions
507 commonly reclassify sites as forest above a tree-cover threshold of 25% (Peterka et al., 2017). Using a
508 conservative threshold of >30% tree cover, 17.6% of Alpine peatlands in our dataset exceeded this level,
509 indicating substantial woody encroachment even under a more strict cut-off. Case studies show similar
510 dynamics: expanding *Pinus* stands on peat in the Jura Mountains have been linked to local drainage and
511 peat cutting (Freléchoux et al., 2000) and temperate peatlands elsewhere have experienced rapid tree
512 densification over recent decades (Habib & Connolly, 2023; Lavoie et al., 2022). The ecological
513 mechanisms by which woody encroachment and other disturbances transform peatlands are well established.
514 Trees and shrubs increase water loss through interception and transpiration, shade bryophyte layers, and
515 alter nutrient cycling—processes that suppress peat-forming mosses and facilitate further tree recruitment
516 (Eppinga et al., 2009; Ohlson et al., 2001; Rietkerk et al., 2004). These feedbacks can lock sites into
517 alternative stable states (e.g., wooded peatland or grassland) and are often accelerated by hydrological
518 modification such as artificial drainage (Sjögren et al., 2007). In mountain regions where livestock
519 husbandry remains widespread, overgrazing and haymaking further alter community composition through
520 selective foraging, nutrient enrichment and trampling (Middleton et al., 2006; Segerström & Emanuelsson,
521 2002; Spitale, 2021).

522 Drainage initiates successional shifts in vegetation and soil microbes that accelerate losses of carbon
523 (Gallego-Sala et al., 2018). These emissions can flip drained peatlands from C sinks to sources, even if
524 encroaching woody vegetation temporarily increases aboveground C fixation (Hommeltenberg et al., 2014;
525 Ward et al., 2007). Although drainage is thus pivotal in degrading mires, the presence of ‘Ditches’ on almost
526 half of the mapped peatlands did not significantly effect FNR across sites, which is surprising. Likewise,
527 ‘Infrastructure’, recorded on ~59% of peatlands, was not associated with significantly higher FNR. We
528 suggest that this likely reflects, i.a., the heterogeneous field implementation (e.g., narrow or infilled ditches
529 at various spatial geometries). Second, a substantial time lag may exist between disturbance and detectable
530 change: ditches may exist long before plant communities shift in ways visible to EO. Furthermore,
531 hydrological effects can extend far beyond mapped ditches. Drawdown from drained margins may penetrate
532 into mapped interiors that appear undrained on orthophotos (Sallinen et al., 2019); hence, mapping only
533 ditches within peatland polygons is likely insufficient to capture all ditch-related degradation.

534 Our model showed a small number of high-confidence detections with strong peatland signatures outside
535 and adjacent to peatland polygons. Given the low FPR, the absolute number of such model–map
536 divergences is small. Where they occur, the characteristic microtopography and vegetation tone/texture of

537 peatlands (in contrast to the surrounding vegetation/land use types) indicate unmapped peatlands (based on
538 visual confirmations) rather than model errors—suggesting fruitful candidates for field checks. Overall, the
539 low FPR suggests that government maps include most peatlands in the European Alps. Nevertheless,
540 identifying even small, unmapped peatlands is important. Recent work shows that even very small “kettle-
541 hole” systems can be C hotspots (Karpińska-Kończak et al., 2024). For biodiversity, incomplete maps may
542 bias conservation networks toward well-known sites and underrepresent small or remote systems (Chytrý
543 et al., 2020; Essl & Steiner, 2017).

544 Whereas intensive field monitoring of selected sites is required to provide spatial degradation patterns in
545 mapped peatlands and to validate the presence of “missing” peatlands, our visual assessment provides
546 strong indications that “false negatives/positives” reliably signal boundary shifts or a spatial pattern of
547 functional decline since the last inventory or not yet mapped sites. Aggregating classification disagreements
548 highlights spatial hotspots of map–model divergence and can guide re-mapping and restoration efforts
549 (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). Whereas global products tend to overlook small,
550 individual Alpine peatlands, our false-negative rates help creating a priority map that emphasizes Alpine
551 regions with a high likelihood of mire degradation. In practice, this priority surface can help government
552 agencies (for example, in Switzerland, where FNR was highest) to: (i) target re-monitoring where mappings
553 are likely outdated (e.g., high FNR in forested or agricultural settings, or recent road/ditch expansion); (ii)
554 refine boundaries where systematic offsets occur (mixed FNR/FPR); and (iii) survey for missed peatlands
555 where consistent model signals lie outside official polygons (high-confidence FPR detections supported by
556 orthophotos). We thus advocate a rolling re-monitoring cycle that uses automated EO detections to cue
557 focused field validation rather than systematic resurveys. Aligned with global initiatives (Austin et al.,
558 2025), this approach offers a practical route to expand monitoring of small, scattered Alpine peatlands and
559 to strengthen their protection.

560 **Conclusion and Outlook**

561 Our multi-sensor, cross-country workflow best detects alpine peatlands when combining Sentinel-2,
562 Sentinel-1, and terrain metrics; Optical indices drive most of the predictive signal, while radar adds
563 complementary but less information consistent with vegetation and moisture controls. Landsat-8 surface
564 temperature and Sentinel-1 contribute little to overall performance and could be omitted to optimize
565 computation time for large areas.

566 Model-map comparisons reveal low false-positive rates, suggesting few unmapped peatlands adjacent to
567 existing polygons, but high false-negative rates—primarily where mapped peatlands show obvious signs of
568 forest encroachment or agricultural use. Roads, houses and ditches do not show a consistent effect, likely

569 reflecting temporal lags. Manual inspection of orthophotos remains essential to interpret both
570 misses/degradation and/or not yet mapped peatlands. Despite limitations such as different peatland
571 classification schemes between countries/regions, temporal mismatches between ground-truth maps and
572 imagery, sub-pixel or intermittent disturbances, and reduced detectability of very small peatlands, our
573 approach is operationally useful. The latter two issues may be resolved by using high-resolution satellite
574 imagery, such as provided by PlanetScope. Model–map overlays transparently separate likely degradation
575 from labelling errors, and aggregated disagreement layers efficiently prioritise regions for field validation
576 where resources are limited.

577 Built on open Earth-observation data and standardised features, the developed workflow is reproducible,
578 scalable, and suited to cross-border approaches. Embedding these products into environmental agency
579 workflows will thus shorten the detection-to-verification loop, accelerate targeted map updates across
580 Alpine regions, and thus focus conservation and restoration efforts where high-elevation peatlands are most
581 at risk.

582

583

584 **Declarations of interest**

585 The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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593 **Author Contributions**

594 **Marian Schönauer:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Validation,
595 Software, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

596 **Elizaveta Avoiani:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation,
597 Formal analysis.

598 **Douglas L. Godbold:** Writing – review & editing.

599 **Boris Rewald:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology,
600 Conceptualization.

601 **Data availability**

602 The data, including spreadsheets, training shapefiles and vectorized predictions were made available at
603 Zenodo:

- 604 • Shapefiles of ground-truth data and predictions: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855356>
605 (Schönauer, 2025)
- 606 • Spreadsheets upon acceptance

607 The script used for analysis was made available at GitHub (URL upon acceptance).

608

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